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(54) **METHOD FOR THE PREVENTION AND/OR THE BIOLOGICAL CONTROL OF WILT CAUSED BY RALSTONIA SOLANACEARUM**

VERFAHREN ZUR PRÄVENTION UND/ODER BIOLOGISCHEN KONTROLLE DER DURCH RALSTONIA SOLANACEARUM VERURSACHTEN VERWELKUNG

PROCÉDÉ DE PRÉVENTION ET/OU DE LUTTE BIOLOGIQUE CONTRE LA FLÉTRISSION CAUSÉE PAR RALSTONIA SOLANACEARUM

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Description**Technical Field**

5 **[0001]** The invention relates to biological control of pathogenic organisms to crop plants. More specifically, the invention relates to a method for the prevention and/or biological control of bacterial wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum*, to bacteriophages useful therefor and to the use of the aforementioned bacteriophages and of compositions containing them for biological control of this bacterium.

10 **Background of the Invention**

[0002] *R. solanacearum* produces bacterial wilt worldwide in more than 200 plant species belonging to more than 50 botanical families, and many of these species susceptible to this pathogen are of agricultural interest. There are also many other crops that are colonized by the bacteria, but do not develop symptoms, which are considered tolerant crops. 15 This bacterium especially attacks staple crops such as potatoes in more than eighty countries, with losses exceeding 950 million dollars. For this reason, it is considered as a potential agent of bioterrorism and in the European Union (EU) as a quarantine organism (Anonymous 2000: Council Directive 2000/29/EC), which is subject to strict prevention and control measures regulated by two European directives (Anonymous 1998, 2006: Council Directive 98/57/EC and Commission Directive 2006/63/EC).

20 **[0003]** *R. solanacearum* presents great intraspecific diversity, and has therefore long been considered a complex of species consisting of four phylogenetic groups or phylotypes. In 2014, after a taxonomic revision, a reclassification of this complex was proposed (Safni et al., 2014). The phylotypes I and III of *R. solanacearum* they have been classified as the new species *R. pseudosolanacearum* and phylotype IV in the new subspecies *R. syzygii* subsp. *indonesiensis*. Phylotype II retains the name of the species *R. solanacearum*.

25 **[0004]** In the text of this document the term "the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*" is used to refer to *R. solanacearum* in studies, data, patents, publications, literature, etc., prior to the taxonomic revision of Safni et al (2014), regardless of whether the name corresponds or not with the current classification. Furthermore, the term "*R. solanacearum*" is used to refer to the species *R. solanacearum* as described after the aforementioned taxonomic revision, i.e. the species is constituted solely by strains of phylotype II.

30 **[0005]** In Spain, as in most EU countries, there have been outbreaks of the disease caused by *R. solanacearum* in several areas, usually in potatoes and in some cases tomatoes. In all cases of outbreaks the eradication measures set out in the relevant legal regulations were implemented. However, this bacterium can survive in the environment, water, soil or other reservoirs (Alvarez et al., 2007, 2008, 2010). Thus, subsequent outbreaks have been associated with irrigation with surface water contaminated with this bacteria (Caruso et al., 2005), as these are one of the main routes of introduction and spread of the pathogen into new areas, which comes through irrigation water. In fact, it described the presence of *R. solanacearum* in various waterways both in Spain and virtually all EU countries. Therefore, the EU Directives prohibit irrigation with water contaminated with this bacteria.

35 **[0006]** This represents a practical problem for the farmer, as the most affected crops are irrigated crops (tomato and potato) and irrigation water is a scarce commodity in Spain and other countries of the Mediterranean basin, where the bacteria are also present. Also in the area where outbreaks of the disease have been detected, host plants cannot be grown over a period of at least 4 years from the detection of an outbreak.

40 **[0007]** The large capacity of survival of *R. solanacearum* in the environment (water, soil or other reservoirs) impedes control. In the past and up to the present moment, control through farming practices and chemical control are being used. Thus, in areas of the world where this pathogen is present in the soil, usually in developing countries, growing host plants is problematic and the most widely used methods of control are farming techniques with varying results. Resistant cultivars have also been obtained, however, resistance may be unstable (Hartman and Elphinstone, 1994).

45 **[0008]** With respect to control via chemical or physical treatments, generally they are not effective. The application of copper compounds, antibiotics and soil fumigants have been used without much success (Lopez and Biosca, 2005), and are also expensive and have a great impact on the environment. Other chemical treatments such as chlorination or physical treatments, such as ultraviolet radiation of water contaminated with bacterial pathogens, have limited effectiveness where particles are present in the water, even if very small (Marco-Noales et al., 2008). Furthermore, it has been shown that both of aforementioned disinfectant treatments can induce various bacteria to enter into the viable but non-culturable state (VBNC) (Oliver et al., 2005 Santander et al, 2012.) Or cause reversible cell damage (McFeters and LeChevallier, 2000). These bacterial cells in the VBNC state or having reversible damage can recover cultivability and pathogenicity after coming into contact with susceptible host plants (Santander et al., 2012). These circumstances demonstrate the need for alternative methods that preferably destroy the bacterial cells.

50 **[0009]** An alternative would be biological control using specific bacteriophages of *R. solanacearum*. This biocontrol strategy has been successful in the treatment of other diseases caused by phytopathogenic bacteria (Jones et al., 2007).

Bacteriophages in general, their isolation and characterization, as well as their use for plant disease control can be considered well known in the prior art (Balogh et al., 2010).

[0010] In that vein, Japanese patent JP4532959-B2 (publication number JP2005278513) describes three types of bacteriophages with bacteriolytic activity on Japanese strains of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* and from 2014 belonging to the new species *R. pseudosolanacearum*. Type 1, with double-stranded DNA genome (dsDNA) of approximately 250 kbp, and types 2 and 3, with a genome of single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) of 4.5 and 6 kbp respectively. Bacteriophages are characterized and distinguished by the size of their genomes and their activity against six strains of bacteria (C319, M4S, Ps29, Ps65, Ps72 and Ps74), all of which are sensitive to type 1 bacteriophages, while the type 2 only lyses one strain (the C319 strain) and type 3 lyses four of the six strains (M4s, Ps29, PS65 and Ps74) and a fifth in one trial (the C319 strain). Trials with restriction endonucleases have only been performed with type 1 bacteriophages and show that its genome (dsDNA) targets *PstI* and *KpnI*, since in the resulting restriction profiles several distinct bands are observed. Finally, the use of two of the three types of bacteriophages (types 1 and 2) to control the disease caused by species formerly known as *Ralstonia solanacearum* (currently *R. pseudosolanacearum*) by addition to soil cultivation where the plant to be protected is growing.

[0011] Japanese Patent JP4862154-B2 arises from a limitation of the above because, as is indicated therein, "it is not enough to control the effect." In this second patent is included a new type of bacteriophage lytic activity against all strains of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* which were tested (only a total of 15 strains) and perform characterization, but do not demonstrate their capacity for biocontrol, since no biocontrol tests were performed on plants with this new type of bacteriophage. In short, the second patent only provides a new type of lytic bacteriophage with a range of hosts that is seemingly larger than previous types.

[0012] Yamada et al (2007) describe the isolation of four types of bacteriophages that infect specific strains of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*, from 2014 belonging to the new species *R. pseudosolanacearum*, from soil samples taken in different areas of Japan. These authors perform structural characterization including a morphological characterization by electron microscopy virions and molecular characterization by restriction analysis of the four types of bacteriophages, and some lytic activity tests with cultured bacteria in Petri dishes. Two types of bacteriophages described are miroviruses, the genus to which all the bacteriophages infecting the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (now *R. pseudosolanacearum*) belong described before publication of the article by Yamada et al, and the other two types are filamentous bacteriophages of the inovirus type. Among other applications, the usefulness of the bacteriophages' lytic activity as biocontrol agents for the eradication of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (now *R. pseudosolanacearum*) in contaminated soils and preventing wilting caused by the bacteria in vegetable crops is suggested, showing preference for bacteriophages capable of infecting a wide range of pathogenic strains, although only testing 15 strains of this host. The only tests with plants included in the aforementioned article referred to observing a plant injected with a strain previously infected with one of the isolated lysogenic bacteriophages, concluding that filamentous phages were not satisfactory for a disease control effect. This same test method has been used in other studies of the same group also with filamentous bacteriophages of the *Inoviridae* family [see Addy et al., 2012 and International Patent Application WO2012/147928], where it is shown that aforementioned method of inoculation, in the case of lysogenic bacteriophage type Φ RSM, leads to the emergence of avirulent strains of *R. solanacearum* that help control the disease caused by the virulent forms of aforementioned bacteria. However, besides the fact that the inoculation tests have only been performed in 5 plants per strain and without repetition [see material and methods Addy et al., 2012], the practical application of this test method in nursery or in the field is highly questionable because the work required to inject each individual plant.

[0013] In another article by the same research group (Fujiwara et al., 2011) test results demonstrating utility as biocontrol agents on the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (currently *R. pseudosolanacearum*) are provided for three lytic phages: two types of bacteriophages of the *Myoviridae* family described by Yamada and collaborators (2007, 2010), Φ RSA1 and Φ RSL1, as well as the effect of other additional bacteriophage Φ RSB1, with was previously isolated (Kawasaki et al., 2009). The latter belongs to the *Podoviridae* family and, like Φ RSA1, is capable of causing lysis in a higher number of strains, up to 13 of 15 strains of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (of which at least 13 are currently classified as *R. pseudosolanacearum*) (Yamada et al., 2007; Kawasaki et al, 2009). It is shown that treatment of the bacteria with Φ RSA1, Φ RSB1 and Φ RSL1 either individually or in possible combinations, except treatment with Φ RSL1 alone, results in a rapid decrease in cell density of the host bacteria, which is only an initial decrease because is followed by the appearance of resistance visible by OD (optical density) in less than 2 days. To avoid such resistance, Fujiwara and colleagues (2011) selected the use of mirovirus Φ RSL1 individually with respect to other combinations with Φ RSA1 and Φ RSB1, although it is noteworthy that this is the lowest bacteriophage lytic potential of the three.

[0014] Tests performed on plants described in the article by Fujiwara et al (2011), all done with Φ RSL1, entailed two treatments with a suspension of aforementioned bacteriophage at high concentrations conducted with a spacing of one month, first to the seed and then to the resulting plants; after two days these plants were individually inoculated with the bacterial suspension by direct contact to the cut tips of the roots (for 30 seconds) and then transplanted. This method of inoculation, like the previous used by these authors in other publications and patents, it is very difficult if not impossible

to implement in nurseries or in cultivated fields. Furthermore, in aforementioned publication the reproducibility of the results is not indicated.

[0015] Fujiwara et al (2011) also describe stability tests on Φ RSL1 on two plants pre-treated with aforementioned bacteriophage and soil in contact therewith, detecting bacteriophages in the roots and in the rhizosphere soil 4 months after inoculation, although it was not verified whether the recovered bacteriophages are of the same type as those inoculated. Also, the effect of temperature on the stability of Φ RSA1, Φ RSB1 and Φ RSL1 was tested in presence and absence of soil (in SM buffer, Tris-HCl, NaCl, MgSO₄ and gelatine). The stability was monitored for only 15 days. At the same temperature, major differences in the stability of the three bacteriophages in the presence of soil were observed. Both in the absence and presence of soil, the differences were greater with increasing temperature but, in the absence of soil, marked differences start from 28°C. After 15 days incubation in the absence of soil at 50°C, 10% of Φ RSL1 bacteriophages survived, Φ RSB1 bacteriophages were not detected after 9 days of incubation, and after 3 days of incubation in the case of Φ RSA1.

[0016] Thus, the work of the Japanese group which includes Yamada, Addy and Fujiwara, show that in some cases and with some bacteriophages that infect the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (now *R. pseudosolanacearum*), can be used as agents for prevention of disease caused by the bacteria. Except in one case, the podovirus Φ RSB1, ruled out by these authors for biocontrol (Fujiwara et al., 2011), bacteriophages described and used in aforementioned tests belong to families *Myoviridae* or *Inoviridae*. In aforementioned tests, the bacteriophages are applied directly to the soil, seedlings or in roots or stems of plants. No evidence of the potential effectiveness of other means of administration of bacteriophages are given, such as perhaps through irrigation water. This is not surprising, because in Japan *R. pseudosolanacearum* has not been detected in natural watercourses, unlike the case in many European countries and in some areas of the US where this type of water is one of the reservoirs and routes of dissemination of *R. solanacearum*.

[0017] Bhunchoth et al. (Bhunchoth et al., 2015) describes the isolation of bacteriophages infecting the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (now *R. pseudosolanacearum*) from tomato fields in Thailand and their experimental use as biocontrol agents. 12 bacteriophages isolated from tomato fields are disclosed, from which 9 phages are podoviruses. Podovirus J2 in combination with another podovirus, Φ RSB2, very efficiently lysed host cells in contaminated soil.

[0018] An article of a Korean group, the group of Ju Young Bae (Bae et al., 2012), also relates to bacterial wilt caused by the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* (now *R. pseudosolanacearum*) and the biocontrol potential of a lytic bacteriophage, PE204, which is characterized by a dsDNA genome similar to that of the members of the *Podoviridae* family.

[0019] The ability to control *R. solanacearum* in water by using bacteriophages has been seen in other studies in some areas of eastern and western Europe. Thus, the summary of the Georgian patent application GEU20041089 suggests neutralization of aforementioned bacteria in plants, soil and water using a mixture of polyvalent bacteriophages in equal proportion.

[0020] The present group of inventors, however, has previously suggested the use of specific bacteriophages of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* in irrigation water to control bacterial wilt caused by aforementioned pathogen (Alvarez et al., 2006a; Alvarez et al, 2006b). The influence of the conditions of watercourses in the survival of the bacteria have been verified, finding that the presence of native microbiota and temperatures of 24°C favoured the disappearance with respect to the temperature of 14°C and sterile water used as a control (Alvarez et al., 2006a). None of these disclosures provides information about the phylotype of the tested strains, so it cannot be aforementioned that these phages could act on the current *R. solanacearum*, consisting of strains phylotype II.

[0021] The group of the present inventors have also reported the isolation of specific lytic bacteriophages of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* from rivers in Spain (Alvarez et al., 2006a, Alvarez et al., 2006b), but without specifying the method of isolation and the specific place of isolation of each. The authors have reported initial data on the characterization of one of them, saying that it seems to show lytic activity between 14°C and 31°C, but not at lower temperatures (9°C) or higher temperatures (32-39°C) even in natural irrigation water pH ranges from 6.5 to 8.2. The initially characterized bacteriophage appears to be specific to the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*, it shows lytic activity on 30 strains of different origins, of which the phylotype has not been disclosed. The bacteriophage showed lytic activity against other bacterial isolates of river water. Aforementioned bacteriophage also results in the reduction of bacterial wilt in tomato plants irrigated with water containing mixtures of bacteriophage and the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*.

[0022] The data obtained by Alvarez and his colleagues support the possibility of using bacteriophages to prevent and/or control bacterial wilt, in particular by addition to irrigation water. However, data released by the group so far do not identify the specific watercourses from which the lytic bacteriophages obtained by them can be isolated. Nor was specific data given on any of aforementioned bacteriophages in order to facilitate the identification via the structural characteristics. Data on the range of temperatures and pH in which aforementioned bacteriophages are active has only been reported for one, which was also claimed to be able to lyse 30 different strains of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*, without specifying the particular strains in which it has proven activity.

[0023] Therefore, there is still a lack of specific lytic bacteriophages which have been established to, individually, be

able to reduce bacterial wilt when added to irrigation water. For the single bacteriophage on which this type of tests have been carried out, reflected in the academic presentation made by the present group of inventors (Alvarez et al, 2006a; Alvarez et al, 2006b), data have not been disclosed to allow identification other than by the lytic activity at different pHs and temperatures and the claim that decreases bacterial wilt in tomato plants, not revealing the genus or family or any concrete data on watercourses in which it is present (and from which it could be isolated) or the specific method of the isolation or the phylotype of the host strains that are affected.

[0024] Thus, neither for bacteriophages isolated by Alvarez et al. or for the bacteriophages whose use is suggested in the Georgian patent application GEU20041089 in the form of polyvalent mixtures, are there available data on survival under natural conditions, in particular on their survival in the conditions of the waters in which they would be used. A central factor in determining the suitability of a bacteriophage as biocontrol agent is precisely the survival under natural conditions. When bacteriophages of phytopathogenic are applied to soil or plants to eliminate aforementioned pathogenic bacteria, the time they can stay active until they find their target cell is the limiting factor in the process, which causes repeated applications of these bacteriophages to be required for effective control. And in the case of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*, its control in watercourses, especially in irrigation water and containers (tanks, storage vessels, reservoirs...) it is important, especially in Europe, because:

- i) the main crops affected by *R. solanacearum* are irrigated (especially potato and tomato),
- ii) there is currently a shortage of water in Spain and other countries of the Mediterranean basin where the pathogen is present,
- iii) there are official prohibitions throughout the EU to use contaminated water for irrigation of host plants (Anonymous, 1998, 2006 water: Council Directive 98/57/EC and Commission Directive 2006/63/EC),
- iv) no control methods available for use in water,
- v) a priority objective of EU policy is the conservation of the environment (Montesinos et al, 2008; Horizon 2020 Program).

[0025] Therefore, it would be desirable to control the populations of bacteria in river water and/or irrigation in a biological treatment that is effective and respectful of the natural environment. And, as was aforementioned previously, it is preferable for the method to result in the death of the bacteria.

[0026] In the case of plant pathogen *R. solanacearum*, the habitats of which are the host plants and soil, a biological agent that is supplied by water must have biological characteristics that allow it to survive in that environment, which is not the usual environment of the bacteria or its specific bacteriophages. If such survival is prolonged and bacteriophages maintain their lytic activity on the host after long periods in water, this further favours applicability in the field as they can be transferred directly by natural and simple means such as water, without needing to encapsulated them or to provide other physical and/or biological means to protect their viability until contact with the target cell. This high survival rate would also facilitate the preparation of a commercial form, which could be in an aqueous medium without requiring refrigeration (or even lower temperatures) to maintain effectiveness.

[0027] However, it should be noted that bacteriophages are obligate intracellular parasites, and as such, require the host cell for perpetuation. Since they reach the cell in different ways, depending on the types of bacteriophages and types of host cells, survival time in the environment is expected in order to allow them to come into contact with the host cell. It is known that this time can vary between different bacteriophages, which requires study in each particular case. For example, significant variations are observed in the survival of bacteriophages the same serotype/genotype (Brion et al., 2002) or even between bacteriophages of aquatic pathogenic fish bacteria, the natural habitat of which is water (Pereira et al., 2011). In the latter case, three months has come to be regarding as good survival time of bacteriophages in water, accepting that bacteriophages displaying increased survival in water are good candidates for the control of bacterial fish diseases in aquaculture (Pereira et al., 2011).

[0028] It should be noted that *R. solanacearum* is a phytopathogenic bacterium whose natural environment is frequently the xylem of plants and soil, but not water. Since it is not an indigenous bacteria to aquatic environments, specific bacteriophages are not expected to have a high water survival rate. In fact, none of the previously mentioned publications and patents describes the viability and specific lytic activity of lytic bacteriophages of the species formerly known as *Ralstonia solanacearum* in environmental water in the absence of host cells.

[0029] And yet, it would be beneficial to have specific lytic bacteriophages against *R. solanacearum*, particularly that show a broad spectrum of strains of that species on which they are active and that also have a high survival rate in water, preferably of at least a month or more, more preferably several months. This could make possible biological treatment of irrigation water contaminated with *R. solanacearum*, using specific bacteriophages of the pathogen, which could prevent or reduce bacterial wilt in polluted areas that may impact susceptible plants. Treatment with these bacteriophages present the usual advantages over chemical treatments, as well as those associated with other treatments of biocontrol, especially with bacteriophages:

- High specificity for the host cell,
- Natural replication only in the host cell,
- Harmless to other living beings, including microbiota beneficial to the plants to be protected,
- Using biological treatment via irrigation water is easier and cheaper than chemical control, and does not require protective measures for staff during application, since it is harmless to humans,
- Lower environmental impact, especially compared to copper compounds and antibiotics used in agriculture, for which many pathogens have developed resistance, reducing the effectiveness of such chemical treatments and also increasing the chemical contamination of soil, plants and fruit,
- Less legal use restrictions, can be applied where chemical control is prohibited,
- Since they are inert in their extracellular state, bacteriophages can be combined with other control strategies and/or biocontrol to increase disease control,
- Easy, low-cost production because they increase their number in the presence of target bacteria,
- Easy adjustment of the dose of bacteriophages to be used depending on the concentration of pathogen to be treated.

[0030] The present invention provides a solution to the problem of the absence of bacteriophages that display a broad spectrum of strains of the bacterium on which they are active and that also have a high survival rate in water, preferably at least one month, or more preferably, of at least several months.

Summary of the Invention

[0031] The present invention is based on isolation, from river water from various regions of Spain, several bacteriophages capable of lysing the bacteria *R. solanacearum*, and the results of structural, functional and molecular characterization, as well as the genomics, from which the following have been established:

- They all belong to the same viral species, the a new species belonging to the *Podoviridae* family,
- They are specific to aforementioned bacteria,
- They are active on a wide range of strains of *R. solanacearum*,
- They are active at different temperatures, pHs, salinity and aeration and in the presence of light,
- They have a high survival rate in water, more than three years, in natural waters of different chemical and pH compositions and at different temperatures, in the absence of the host, maintaining their lytic capacity after such long periods,
- They are able to decrease wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum* if plants are irrigated with water containing at least one of aforementioned bacteriophages.

[0032] Tests were able to verify that these features are also shared by the bacteriophage for which a partial functional characterization (lytic activity in liquid medium at different temperatures and pHs, initial host range and ability to control wilting in plants) was already described in previous work of the present group of inventors (Alvarez et al., 2006a, Alvarez et al., 2006b), without the specific origin, method of isolation, survivability having been described and without a molecular and genomic characterization having been made that would allow taxonomic classification, for which until now the family to which it belongs is unknown.

[0033] Their high specificity, the wide range of strains they are active on and, most particularly, their high survival rate in water, makes all these bacteriophages very suitable agents for biocontrol of *R. solanacearum* in water in natural watercourses and/or irrigation water and reservoirs, and for the prevention and/or treatment of wilt produced by aforementioned bacteria in plants. This is because maintaining lytic activity after long periods favours the use in field crops or in greenhouses or nurseries or in other situations, to which they can be transferred directly via water, a natural and simple way, without encapsulating them or any other physical, chemical and/or biological means to protect the viability until contact with the target cell. Thus, implementation costs are reduced since the number of applications required over time is reduced, the long-term efficiency of the product is increased in agricultural systems in which it is intended to be used, and outbreaks of disease caused by *R. solanacearum* can be prevented and combated more effectively. Thus, control agents of *R. solanacearum* based on these bacteriophages have a greater "added value" than other products for farmers and nursery keepers, the major potential consumers of aforementioned product.

[0034] In addition, as it was previously stated, such very high survival rate in water of the bacteriophages of the invention, while maintaining the lytic capacity after long periods in aforementioned medium in the absence of a host was not expected for a specific bacteriophage of a bacterium whose natural environment is not water as it is the case of *R. solanacearum*, and this ability has not been observed in other specific lytic bacteriophages of aforementioned bacteria, isolated from natural watercourses of Spain by the present inventors.

[0035] Therefore, in a first aspect, the invention relates to a bacteriophage able to lyse cells of *Ralstonia solanacearum* selected from the group of:

- a) vRsoP-WF2 (DSM 32039), vRsoP-WM2 (DSM 32040), vRsoP-WR2 (DSM 32041), or
 b) a podovirus whose genome has the sequence of SEQ ID NO:1 (corresponding to vRsoP-WF2), SEQ ID NO:2 (corresponding to vRsoP-WM2) or SEQ ID NO:3 (corresponding to vRsoP-WR2).

- 5 **[0036]** Hereinafter, the term "bacteriophage of the invention" is used to refer to any one of these bacteriophages.
[0037] In another aspect, the invention relates to a composition comprising at least one of the bacteriophages of the invention, or combinations of them. This composition will be considered a composition of the present invention.
[0038] In a further aspect, the invention relates to the use of at least one of the bacteriophages of the invention, or combinations, to control *R. solanacearum* in natural watercourses, channelled water streams, natural reservoirs of water, irrigation water and irrigation water reservoirs, by adding one or more of these bacteriophages to irrigation water or reservoirs .
 10 **[0039]** In another aspect, related to the previous aspect, the invention relates to the use of at least one of the bacteriophages of the invention, or combinations, or compositions of the invention to control *R. solanacearum* in soil by addition of one or more of the aforementioned bacteriophages or a composition of the invention to aforementioned soil through irrigation water with which the soil is watered, or pre-treated with the aforementioned bacteriophages or aforementioned composition.
 15 **[0040]** In an additional aspect, the invention relates to a method for preventing or controlling bacterial wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum* in plants, comprising the steps of:
 20 a) adding a composition to the water to be used for watering plants, comprising bacteriophages belonging to at least one of the bacteriophages of the invention, or combinations;
 b) watering plants with aforementioned water.

- 25 **[0041]** As indicated previously, the term "*Ralstonia solanacearum*," without reference to the previous meaning of this term is used in the invention to refer to the species *R. solanacearum* as described after the last taxonomic review, i.e. the species constituted by phylotype II strains. Conversely, when the term "species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*" is used, it refers to the bacteria that were considered to be within the term *R. solanacearum* in studies, data, patents, publications, literature, etc., prior to the taxonomic revision of Safni et al. (2014), regardless of whether the name corresponds or not to the current classification.
 30 **[0042]** Accordingly, the present invention, i.e. the "method for the prevention and/or biological control of wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum*, by means of the use of bacteriophages useful therefor and compositions", refers to *R. solanacearum* as described after taxonomic revision of Safni et al. (2014). The three inventions of other authors mentioned in this document refer to the "species previously known as *R. solanacearum*" that, in cases where information is available (patent documents, publications, etc.), it mostly refers to strains reclassified as the new species *R. pseudosolanacearum*.

35 Brief Description of the Figures

- [0043]**
- 40 Fig. 1 shows photographs of the culture medium dishes from the lytic activity tests on the bacteriophages isolated from river water against *Ralstonia solanacearum*. Darker areas correspond to areas of lysis and/or isolated plaques, which are bacteriophage breeding areas in the bacterial lawn, which allow the lysis of the bacteria to be observed in the culture medium, the massive growth of the aforementioned bacterium being seen in whitish and opaque areas.
 45 Fig. 2 shows a photograph of a culture medium dish with bacterial lawn from strain IVIA 1602.1 of *R. solanacearum* on which lysis tests were performed. In each quadrant, the bacteriophage contained in the suspension added to the bacterial lawn is indicated; the location of the control quadrant without bacteriophages (upper left quadrant, marked with the name of the bacterial strain) is also indicated.
 Fig. 3 shows a photograph of the bacteriophages of the present invention obtained by transmission electron microscopy after negative staining. It is observed that they present a non-enveloped, polygonal head (40 to 60 nm in diameter depending on the bacteriophage) and a short tail.
 50 Fig. 4 is a photograph obtained after subjecting to electrophoresis the samples in which digestion of the DNA of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 or vRsoP-WR2 (as indicated at the top of the photograph) had been carried out with various restriction enzymes indicated above each column. The columns at the extreme right and left ends correspond to the pattern of molecular weights (M): λ phage DNA digested with *HindIII*.
 55 Fig. 5 shows the area in which the sequence corresponding to the vRsoP-WM2 bacteriophage presents an insertion of 468 nucleotides to the sequences corresponding to the bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2 and vRsoP-WR2, as well as areas close to this sequence. The presence of a hyphen in a sequence indicates a position where a nucleotide is absent in the aforementioned sequence with respect to one of or both of the other sequences, such absence

allowing continued alignment in the same area. In the lower line below the corresponding sequence lines, the presence of an asterisk indicates coincidence between the nucleotides situated at that position in the three sequences.

Fig. 6 shows the genomic organization of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2, and vRsoP-WR2 as compared to bacteriophage T7. In various shades of grey or with weaves of parallel lines in different directions, the location of functional open reading frames (ORFs) that have been identified using the BLAST tool is indicated, as specified in the legends in the lower part of the figure. It is noted that the three bacteriophages possess a genomic organization and expression of the ORFs similar to bacteriophage T7 in part of the genome.

Fig. 7 shows the survival curves of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2, at incubated at 14°C in the absence of host cells in water from the Tormes river (panel A, top) and the Turia River (panel B, bottom). Survival is expressed as the base 10 logarithm of the plaque forming units detected per millilitre (PFU/ml) in samples taken at the times indicated on the x/y graph.

Fig. 8 shows a graph of the lytic activity of the bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2 added to an initial concentration of 10^3 plaque forming units per millilitre (PFU/ml) in sterile river water, to which 10^6 colony forming units per millilitre (CFU/ml) of *Ralstonia solanacearum* were added. A decrease within time of the CFU/ml corresponding to the bacteria (expressed in the form of the base 10 logarithm, points indicated with a filled circle) and an increase in PFU/ml corresponding to the bacteriophage (also expressed as the base 10 logarithm, points indicated with a filled square) were observed.

Fig. 9 shows an illustrating scheme of the experimental procedure of the use of the bacteriophages of the invention on irrigation water developed by the present inventors for the ability to control bacterial wilt. At the bottom, photographs of the condition of the plants at the beginning of the test (time zero, top row of photographs) and after 1 month (1 month, bottom row of photographs) are shown for each of the combinations of *R. solanacearum* and the bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2 indicated.

Fig. 10 shows a bar graph in which reduction of bacterial wilt, expressed as a percentage, in two different trials in tomato plants are shown. Experiment (Exp.) 1, bacteriophage concentration: 10^9 plaque forming units per millilitre (PFU/ml) and Exp. 2 bacteriophage concentration: 10^6 PFU/ml. In both experiments, the concentration of bacteria was 10^5 colony forming units per millilitre (CFU/ml). Vertical frame bars correspond to those plants treated only with bacteria, without bacteriophages; bars without weaving correspond to plants treated with bacteria and bacteriophage at the indicated concentrations; bars with horizontal weaving correspond to plants treated with bacteria and 1/10 dilutions of the aforementioned concentrations of bacteriophages.

Fig. 11 shows a bar graph that represents reduction of bacterial wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum*, expressed as a percentage, in trials where tomato plants were watered with water containing the combinations of bacteria (Rsol) and bacteriophage indicated under the bars. The four cases located further to the right correspond to irrigation water with binary combinations (from left to right, vRsoP-WF2 with vRsoP-WM2, vRsoP-WF2 with vRsoP-WR2, or vRsoP-WM2 with vRsoP-WR2) or tertiary combinations (vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2) of bacteriophages with the bacteria.

Detailed Description of the Invention

[0044] As mentioned hereinbefore, the invention relates to novel specific bacteriophages of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (bacteriophages of the invention), the use of at least one of the bacteriophages of the invention, or combinations, for *R. solanacearum* control in natural watercourses, natural water reservoirs, irrigation water and irrigation water reservoirs, by adding one or more of these bacteriophages to the aforementioned water or reservoirs; also it refers to the use of these bacteriophages to control *R. solanacearum* in soil, by adding one or more of these bacteriophages to the aforementioned soil via treated irrigation water; and a method for preventing or controlling bacterial wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum* in plants, a composition is added to water to be used for watering plants, the aforementioned composition comprising at least one of the bacteriophages known as vRsoP-WF2 (DSM 32039), vRsoP-WM2 (DSM 32040) or vRsoP-WR2 (DSM 32041), or combinations, and the aforementioned plants are watered with the aforementioned treated water.

[0045] In the present application, the word "phage" is used as an abbreviation for the word "bacteriophage" with the same meaning. Therefore, hereinafter the two terms will be used interchangeably. "Bacteriophage" refers to a virus capable of infecting bacteria, either by producing lysis (lytic cycle) or by inserting itself into the genome and replicating itself therewith without causing lysis (lysogenic cycle).

[0046] The bacteriophages of the invention have been isolated from river water from various regions of Spain, specifically Badajoz, Salamanca and the Alpujarras (Granada).

[0047] Morphological characterization by electron microscopy and molecular characterization by DNA restriction analysis have shown that the virions belong to the *Podoviridae* family (specifically, the genus of T7-like viruses), a family of which so far only one bacteriophage has been described with lytic activity against the species formerly known as *Ralstonia solanacearum*, i.e. the bacteriophage Φ P5B1, described by Fujiwara et al (Fujiwara et al., 2011) and which has a larger

genome than the bacteriophages of the present invention, whose genome does not exceed 41,000 base pairs (bp) in any of the three cases (see Table 2), while the Φ P5B1 genome has a size of 43,077 bp. Furthermore, the three inventions of other authors mentioned in the present application, relating to the use of bacteriophages to control *R. solanacearum* refer to the species formerly known as *Ralstonia solanacearum*, and, where information is available (patent documents, scientific publications, etc.), it can be confirmed that the strains dealt with are mostly reclassified as the new species *R. pseudosolanacearum*.

[0048] Therefore, the bacteriophages of the present invention do not belong to one of the most common families of bacteriophages lytic for the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*, i.e. *Myoviridae*, but rather to a different family. In addition, they appear to be part of the same species, different from other species of T7-like viruses described so far. The discovery of viruses belonging to a new species of bacteriophages which attack *R. solanacearum* is an unexpected event.

[0049] The genome of any of the three bacteriophages of the present invention appears to have recognition targets for PstI restriction enzyme, which does not result in digestion of them, which represents a difference with lytic bacteriophages of Japanese Patent JP4532959- B2, wherein they are digested by the enzyme.

[0050] Thus, in the present invention are provided first data to identify the three bacteriophages of the present invention and distinguish them from any known bacteriophage, such as the family to which they belong, genus, the assignment of all of them to a single species, the sequence of the genome and distinctive restriction profile, obtained with several enzymes after digestion of the genome (see Examples 1 and 2, and Fig. 3, 4, 5 and 6). The isolation method used and a source of each is further described. Additionally, for clear definition, the deposit number issued by the Leibniz-Institut DSMZ-Deutsche Sammlung von Mikro-Organismen und Zellkulturen GmbH is provided, as authority for international deposit under the Budapest Treaty for each of the bacteriophages.

[0051] In addition to the structural characterization (morphological characterization of the viral particles and genomic characterization), in the present application the functional characterization (physiological and lytic) of the isolated bacteriophage is also described. As noted previously, one of the important characteristics for a biocontrol agent to be effective is to be shown to act on a wide range of strains. As shown hereinafter in the Examples section of the present application, the data previously described by Alvarez et al (Alvarez et al., 2006a, Alvarez et al., 2006b) were confirmed for a bacteriophage that was known to have been isolated from a watercourse in Spain that had not been specifically identified and for which insufficient structural data had been provided to ascribe them to a family and, much less, to a genus and specific species. In particular, the lytic capacity was confirmed for 30 strains that, at the time, were all considered to belong to the same species, i.e. the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum*, the phylotype of which was unknown, and the pH and temperature ranges in which it showed activity: between 14°C and 31°C, and a pH range of 6.5 to 8.2. These data correspond to the bacteriophage referred to in this application as vRsoP-WF2. It has been found that the other two bacteriophages of the present invention, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 exhibit lytic capacity for the same strains of *Ralstonia solanacearum*, are active in the same ranges of pH and temperature, thus expanding the aforementioned characterization to the three bacteriophages of the present invention. The same results were obtained with mixtures of two of the bacteriophages (vRsoP-WF2 with vRsoP-WM2, vRsoP-WF2 with vRsoP-WR2, or WM2-vRsoP with vRsoP-WR2) or the combination of all three (vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2). Thus, mixtures comprising combinations of these bacteriophages as well as the compositions comprising at least one of the bacteriophages of the present invention are a possible embodiment of the compositions of the present invention.

[0052] The specificity for *Ralstonia solanacearum* was also confirmed, no lytic activity being observed with bacteria isolated from river water with which tests were conducted, or with strains of other species of pathogenic plant bacteria. Again, these data are valid both for the three bacteriophages of the present invention and for combinations.

[0053] Therefore, the three bacteriophages separately, as well as combinations, fulfil the desirable characteristics for biological control agents such as high specificity by the host cell, and not posing a risk to the microbiota of water, soil or plants; being specific against *Ralstonia solanacearum*. Nor they pose a threat to the health of humans, animals or plants, being bacteriophages viruses that only infect bacteria. They are active also in a pH range compatible with the characteristics of different watercourses of Spain, and in a range compatible with the characteristics temperatures. This supports the use of bacteriophages of the present invention, individually or as combinations, and of compositions comprising such bacteriophages, to control *R. solanacearum*, whether in water from natural watercourses such as rivers, streams or creeks, natural reservoirs of water such as lakes, lagoons, ponds, springs and underground accumulations, artificial water reservoirs and dams, covered storage vessels, tanks, ponds (with or without surface covers), wells, irrigation water in general, or reservoirs of irrigation water as well as the aforementioned natural or artificial reservoirs.

[0054] In that sense, the field data collected by the present inventors on natural waters contaminated with *R. solanacearum* in different Spanish autonomous communities reveal that in the summer months (when the bacteria in water is detected and prohibits its use for irrigation) the highest daytime temperatures of these waters are between 13°C and 17°C and decrease at night. For example, in Salamanca and Guadalajara sampled water temperatures vary between 14°C and 4°C. In addition, in countries in central and northern Europe with environmental water contaminated with *R. solanacearum* temperatures are lower in the summer months. Therefore, the range of activity observed for the bacteri-

ophages of the present invention is compatible with use in natural watercourses, particularly in Spain. So is the pH range of action. However, it is not easy to add bacteriophages to a river watercourse in sufficient amount to achieve effective control of microorganisms therein, especially in the particular place where this water will be drawn for irrigation, as bacteriophages will be very diluted and will be carried along watercourse so that although their survival time is very high, such use does not favour bacteriophages to come into contact with the host cell in the section of watercourse that may be of interest, unless bacteriophages are used in short watercourses and/or watercourses with reduced flow, such as rivulets, brooks and artificial pipes, especially those leading to a reservoir where the water will stay for a longer time. Therefore, it is preferred that use should take place in a natural or artificial water reservoir, such as lakes, lagoons, ponds, streams, reservoirs, covered vessels, tanks, ponds (with or without surface covering) or wells. In them, if contamination with *R. solanacearum* is suspected, it is easier to estimate the extent of such contamination and determine the amount or concentration of bacteriophages to add depending thereon. In any case, it is preferred that the water in the reservoir should be maintained at a temperature in the temperature range of 4°C and 30°C inclusive, interval in which the bacteriophages of the present invention survive prolonged periods, keeping their lytic activity, both alone and as part of compositions containing at least one of them. This temperature range also comprises the ambient temperatures of survival and/or multiplication of the pathogen *Ralstonia solanacearum*, i.e. the environmental range of 4°C and 24°C, so that the lytic activity of the bacteriophages of the present invention is effective at the temperatures that such bacteria presents a real threat of development of disease in crops. Since temperatures approaching 30°C are not common in reservoirs of environmental water, and taking into account fluctuations in daily and seasonal environmental temperature, conditions where the average water temperature in the reservoir is between 4°C and 24°C inclusive are preferred.

[0055] It should be noted that the tests described in Example 4 of the present application confirm the applicability of bacteriophages of the present invention via irrigation water and the usefulness in reducing damage caused by *R. solanacearum* wilting in plants. That is why the present invention also provides a method for preventing or controlling wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum* in a plant, comprising the steps of adding to the water be used to water the plant a composition comprising at least one of the bacteriophages of the present invention, or combinations, and watering the plant with the aforementioned treated water.

[0056] The proposal of pre-treatment of irrigation water before use for irrigation is an option not considered in previous studies of Japanese authors discussed hereinbefore and is an option of great interest, since the main crops affected by *R. solanacearum* are irrigated crops. Thus, although it is compatible with the invention that plant cultivation may be carried out in any of the conditions under which cultivation is possible, a possible embodiment of the invention which may be very important use on plants growing in a field, in a nursery, in a greenhouse or any other type of substrate, or hydroponics, where it can be easy to plan and implement the method of the invention within the irrigation system and also do so in ways that benefit many plants simultaneously. Moreover, but perfectly compatible with the aforementioned embodiment, within the possible application to any crop of a species susceptible and/or tolerant to *R. solanacearum*, one embodiment of the invention of great interest is that in which the plant is a species belonging to the family of the *Solanaceae* (*Solanaceae* family) and in particular one in which the plant is selected from among tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*), potatoes (the two crops most frequently affected) (*Solanum tuberosum*), sweet peppers (*Capsicum annum*) or aubergines (*Solanum melongena*). The application of the method of the invention is perfectly compatible whether the plant is in a growing area dedicated to plants of a single species, or growing areas where there are plants of different species, usually with specific sections for each, as is the case of traditional orchards, usually with an irrigation system common to them all and a common irrigation water reservoir. The characteristics of the bacteriophages of the present invention allow for individual application (plant by plant), as is the case with the applications proposed by Japanese authors and with other biocontrol agents is not necessary, to be unnecessary.

[0057] Irrigation can be performed by any known system, such as traditional systems of partial or total flooding, drip irrigation, subsurface irrigation via perforated pipes, by exudation via porous pipes, or spray irrigation.

[0058] As discussed above, it is desirable that, prior to irrigation, the water which the composition with one or more bacteriophages of the present invention will be added to should be maintained at a temperature in the range of 4°C and 24°C which can be considered a usual environmental range, although, as bacteriophages of the invention are active up to a temperature of 31°C, this range can be extended to the range of 4°C and 30°C inclusive, although the latter value is unusual in environmental water reservoirs. As discussed above, conditions where the average water temperature in the reservoir is between 4°C and 24°C inclusive are considered suitable, given the daily and seasonal fluctuations of ambient temperature.

[0059] It is also desirable that the water pH should be in the range of 6.5 to 9.0 (both inclusive) to favour the lytic activity of the bacteriophage of the present invention.

[0060] For the same reasons discussed above, it is preferable that, prior to irrigation of the plant with water, irrigation water should stay in a reservoir, natural or artificial, from the time when the composition comprising one or more bacteriophages of the present invention is added; this approach is consistent with the addition of the bacteriophages when the water is not necessarily in such reservoir, but it is a watercourse that feeds or pours into the reservoir, especially when it is a pipe or a natural watercourse with a low flow rate that flows off of a natural watercourse with a high flow rate

or a large reservoir, natural or artificial, such as a lake or a dam reservoir.

[0061] As for the reservoir itself, can be a storage vessel with or without surface coverage, including tank-type or pond-type; it can also be a natural accumulations of water, such as those that occur in the upwelling of certain springs, or artificial, natural or semi-natural wells as those formed in certain natural cavities, which are accessed by man at a later time.

[0062] On the other hand, it is important to note, as previously commented that one of the key points that determine the effectiveness of bacteriophages as biocontrol agents is their survival in the environmental conditions in which they are intended to be applied. In general, survival of the bacteriophages outside the host, as discussed previously, is extremely variable and depends on the particular nature of each bacteriophage, being strongly influenced by the surrounding environment, by conditions such as pH of the medium, temperature or sunlight (Iriarte et al., 2007). Because sunlight is a factor that often adversely affects the survival of bacteriophages under natural conditions, in considering the use in surface water, it is important for them to survive adequately in the presence of this factor. In this regard, the bacteriophages of the invention were isolated from different Spanish watercourses exposed to different levels of sunlight, unlike Japanese bacteriophages isolated from soil and plant material. Moreover, as bacteriophages of the invention were isolated from water samples in which host cells were present, the unexpected survival in water in the absence of host cells was unknown.

[0063] For all these reasons, survival of the bacteriophages isolated by the present inventors is considered an important factor, nearly a crucial feature that is an important advantage for use as a biocontrol agent in water. As described below in Example 3, the aforementioned survival was tested in the absence of the host cell in natural water from two Spanish rivers (the Tormes River in Salamanca and the Turia River in Valencia) of different chemical composition and pH, and at different temperatures. These two types of water show substantial differences in the main physico-chemical parameters referenced in the composition : specifically with the water of the Turia River values were comparatively 100 times higher in Mn, 10 times higher in Fe, between 5 and 10 times higher in chlorides and triple in nitrates; with water from the Tormes River values being approximately 4 times higher in phosphate; the average values of pH were around 8.13 in the water from the Turia River and 7.36 in the water from the Tormes river. Temperature ranges of water ranged from 3.5°C to 20.9°C for the Tormes River and from 11.5°C to 22.0°C for the water from the Turia River, i.e. temperature ranges for both environmental waters are within the temperature values used for testing survival of the bacteriophages, which were: 4°C, 14°C and 24°C, and the pH values were 7.2 for water from the Tormes River and 8.1 for the water from the Turia River. Of these rivers, the Tormes River is contaminated with *R. solanacearum* and the use of the water is prohibited for irrigation, while contamination has not been observed in the Turia River so far. For tests of the present invention, the aforementioned natural water was filtered through a 0.22 μm filter and sterilized, so that survival tests were performed in the absence of the host. As demonstrated in Example 3, the three bacteriophages of the present invention were active and at high levels of lytic activity for more than 5 months, longer than three months considered good survival period for bacteriophages of aquatic bacteria that affected fish and which are therefore in their natural environment (Pereira et al., 2011). This high survival was observed at the three temperatures tested (4°C, 14°C and 24°C), which were intended to cover the environmental range of interest for use in watercourses and natural reservoirs of water, artificial reservoirs and irrigation water. Subsequently, as mentioned in Example 3, the test was continued, and it was found that, after 3 years in natural water, they remain active. This long period of survival with maintenance of lytic activity is unexpected and surprising, particularly for a lytic bacteriophage of *R. solanacearum* because it is not a native bacteria from aquatic environments, but rather its natural environment is the xylem of plants and often the ground, and it was not expected that this bacteriophages specific of such bacteria would present a high survival rate in water outside the host. In fact, in the studies of Fujiwara et al (Fujiwara et al., 2011), for example, stability was monitored only for 15 days, in which clear differences were observed among the stability of the three bacteriophages tested, more pronounced in a buffer than in the presence of soil, with marked differences observed in the survivability of the two bacteriophages of the *Myoviridae* family, ΦRSL1 and ΦRSA1 .

[0064] As discussed previously, survival outside the host varies greatly between different bacteriophages, even among those belonging to the same serotype/genotype (Brion et al., 2002) or even among those who share a common natural habitat such as water (Pereira et al., 2011), habitat in which survival of aquatic bacteriophages of at least three months previously was considered a suitable characteristic for selecting good candidates for the control of bacterial fish diseases transmitted via water. Thus, the survival of the bacteriophages isolated by the present inventors was not predictable at all, especially considering that not even the family to which they belong was known and a high survival rate in water was not expected, since the usual habitat of its host are plants and soil, not water.

[0065] Therefore, the survival results in the absence of the host are noteworthy of the bacteriophages of the invention obtained at 24°C because the previous results of the present inventors in survival studies of *R. solanacearum* in which lytic activity of other bacteriophages was tested in the presence of the aforementioned host bacteria indicated that the temperature of 24°C promotes the rate of disappearance of the pathogen with respect to a temperature of 14°C (Alvarez et al., 2007). However, at a temperature of 14°C, the bacteriophages of the invention maintain lytic activity on the host in natural water even after three years of the absence, and it has been observed that, in conditions similar to natural conditions, studies by the present inventors with other bacteriophages of this pathogen, lysis also causes a significant

reduction of the populations of this bacterium (Alvarez et al., 2007). In addition, 14°C is a temperature closer to those recorded in most aquatic habitats where the pathogen has been detected in Spain and other European countries.

5 [0066] Moreover, it is noteworthy that it is common conserve biocontrol agents, prior to their use, at low temperatures, preferably at 4°C, but they can also be stored at 14°C, as well as 24°C. Therefore, it is noteworthy that the bacteriophages of the present invention remain active and at high levels at all three test temperatures for more than 5 months and the survival with lytic activity can be as long as a period of three years.

10 [0067] Therefore, a particularly novel feature of the bacteriophages of the present invention is the survival for more than 5 months in natural water in the absence of the host cell. This is an adequate and very advantageous feature for a biological control agent, which must have features that enable it to survive in the medium in which it is intended to be applied, in this case, water.

15 [0068] As a result, it is compatible with the use of the method and use of the present invention that the composition containing bacteriophages should be maintained during storage and/or use, preferably at a temperature in the range from 4°C to 24°C, inclusive, which can be considered a regular environmental range, however, since bacteriophages of the invention are active up to 31°C, this range may extend to a range from 4°C to 30°C inclusive, despite the latter value not being usual in environmental water reservoirs. As discussed above, an average temperature of the water in the reservoir from 4°C to 24°C inclusive, given the daily and seasonal fluctuations of ambient temperature, is also considered to be a suitable condition. This enables the compositions of the present invention to be easily preserved for a long time prior to their use in the form of suspensions in which the bacteriophages are in an aqueous vehicle which can be water (environmental, natural, distilled, previously sterilized, or subjected to another usual treatment for aqueous vehicles) or an aqueous solution (such as sterile saline, phosphate buffered saline, etc.) and ready to use and apply directly where needed. Therefore, the compositions of the present invention may comprise any carrier or excipient agronomically acceptable, and may be in liquid form, e.g. as an aqueous suspension, which can be prepared in water or in an aqueous solution and/or dilutions. In this way, they can be used to control *R. solanacearum* and can be applied with the method of prevention or treatment of wilt caused by the aforementioned bacteria and can be therefore ready for direct use from the stored and marketed form.

25 [0069] The high survival rate, with maintained lytic activity on the host, of the bacteriophages of the present invention, favours the use in the field because they can be transferred directly via water, a natural and simple way, without encapsulating or adding other physical, chemical and/or biological mediums to protect their viability until coming in contact with the target cell. This facilitates the production process, lowers costs and eliminates the need for complex formulations for implementation as well as the addition of chemicals to the environment. Thus, the high survival rate of the bacteriophages in water in the absence of the target cell reduces the implementation costs by decreasing the number of uses required over time, and increases long-term product efficiency in the agricultural systems where they are intended to be applied, and can thus more effectively prevent outbreaks of disease caused by *R. solanacearum*. All this leads to a product with more "added value" for farmers and nursery keepers, the major potential consumers of the aforementioned product, i.e. the bacteriophages of the present invention and/or compositions comprising them.

30 [0070] Moreover, this high survival in natural water while in the extracellular state facilitates combination with other control strategies (chemical and/or physical, and even biological) for the same plant pathogen or others, which may be an additional optional step of the method of the present invention. The method of the present invention is also compatible with the use of copper compounds, antibiotics and/or soil fumigants, whose application to the soil where plant is growing can also be considered an additional optional step of the method of the present invention.

35 [0071] The present invention is also compatible with additional use not only an agent of chemical or physical control, but rather as one or more additional biological control agents other than any of the bacteriophages of the present invention (other microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi and other bacteriophages, etc.). One possibility is any of the lytic or lysogenic bacteriophages previously known, which have activity against the aforementioned bacteria. For use, the additional agent may be further comprised in a composition of the present invention, or may be applied separately.

40 [0072] Although the preferred form of the compositions of the present invention is the liquid form, in aqueous medium, especially when applied to water to control *R. solanacearum* and/or preventing or reducing bacterial wilt caused by the aforementioned bacteria in plants which are to be irrigated with the aforementioned water, other forms of the composition are also compatible with the invention, especially those known to those skilled in the art for the conservation of bacteriophages, such as in a lyophilized form (which facilitates preservation at room temperature) or as a refrigerated and/or frozen aqueous suspension, preferably from 4°C to -20°C, and even lower temperatures, such as -20°C to -80°C.

45 [0073] As already mentioned, the compositions of the present invention may contain one of three bacteriophages whose isolation and morphological and genomic characterization is described in the present application (vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 or vRsoP-WR2), or combinations (vRsoP-WF2 and vRsoP-WM2, vRsoP-WF2 and vRsoP-WR2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2, or vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2). The tests performed and described in Example 4 suggest that combinations, either two of or all three of the bacteriophages of the present invention are more effective than the use of the bacteriophages separately, so they may be a good choice for use against *Ralstonia solanacearum* in water to be treated, and particularly in water that is to be used for irrigation in order to prevent or reduce wilt caused

by this bacteria. In compositions with combinations of several bacteriophages, each may be at the same concentration as in Example 4 of the present application, but different concentrations are also compatible with the invention.

[0074] Moreover, an advantage to consider of using the combination of two or more bacteriophages of the present invention is that mixtures prevent the appearance of strains of *R. solanacearum* that are resistant to the lytic action of any one of them.

[0075] Regarding the total concentration of bacteriophages in the compositions of the present invention, there are no limitations except those imposed for chemical reasons, resulting in the suspension being saturated and bacteriophages precipitating or settling. However, in practice, this is highly unlikely. One option is for the total concentration of bacteriophages of the invention to range between 10^5 and 10^9 plaque forming units per millilitre (PFU/ml), which are concentrations that have been tested in the Examples section of the present application and which can also be a suggested range of concentrations in order to choose the final concentration of bacteriophages desired to be present in the irrigation water. However, concentrations may be higher or lower than those included in that range, with concentrations of 10^3 PFU/ml being able to be maintained and/or used as in section 4.1 of Example 4, or even lower, as the present inventors have obtained lysis data in liquid medium with bacteriophages of the present invention at concentrations of about 10^2 PFU/ml. Thus, the range 10^2 to 10^9 PFU/ml or 10^3 to 10^9 PFU/mL are also possible concentration ranges of the compositions of the present invention or the conditions of action of the bacteriophages of the present invention, as well as other upper or lower limits, since the bacteriophages multiply inside the bacteria.

[0076] As far as the different bacteriophages of the present invention, under the envisaged use and/or maintenance conditions, survival data may lead to a preference for vRsoP-WM2, while macrotests carried out on plants described in Example 4, specifically on tomato plants, can lead to a preference for vRsoP-WR2, because in such tests a greater reduction in bacterial wilt was observed from applying this bacteriophage individually with respect to the other two bacteriophages of the present invention.

[0077] The invention will now be explained in more detail by the Examples and Figures described hereinafter.

Examples

- Example 1. Origin and Isolation of the Bacteriophages.

[0078] Lytic bacteriophages against *R. solanacearum* were isolated from several rivers of Castilla-Leon, Extremadura and Andalusia, in the vicinity of fields affected by bacterial wilt. A selection of these bacteriophages was purified and their lytic activity was tested in the laboratory against *R. solanacearum*, as shown in Fig. 1.

[0079] Among them, three bacteriophages (vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2), from different origins, were chosen for further characterization.

- vRsoP-WF2: isolated from the Tormes River in the vicinity of Salamanca.
- vRsoP-WM2: isolated from the Cayo River in the province of Badajoz.
- vRsoP-WR2: isolated from the Yator River in the area of the Alpujarras, in the province of Granada.

[0080] The three bacteriophages were purified via successive plaque passages in general LPGA medium (yeast extract [5g] - peptone [5 g] - glucose [10 g] - agar [20 g], dissolved in distilled water [1 litre]; the glucose is sterilized by filtration and subsequently added to the rest of the medium sterilized by autoclaving) with host cells of a standard strain of *R. solanacearum* (IVIA 1602.1 strain, deposited at the French Collection of Plant-associated Bacteria [CFBP] under CFBP number 4944 and at the DSMZ free access collection under the number DSM 100387). This method is also preferred for amplification of any of the aforementioned bacteriophages of the present invention on a solid medium.

[0081] Once purified, the lytic activity, pH and temperature range, and range of hosts of them were characterized as described hereinafter.

1.1. Temperature Range.

[0082] The lytic activity observed of the characterized bacteriophages against the selected strain of *R. solanacearum* (IVIA-1602.1) is observed between 14°C and 31°C in all three cases.

[0083] Within this range, the routine incubation temperature of the bacteriophages to multiply in the host, both on solid medium and in liquid medium, under laboratory conditions, is between 28-30°C, because they are the values that are considered optimal for the growth of *R. solanacearum* in these conditions.

[0084] Mixtures of two (vRsoP-WF2 - vRsoP-WM2, vRsoP-WF2 - vRsoP-WR2, vRsoP-WM2 - vRsoP-WR2) or all three bacteriophages (vRsoP-WF2 - vRsoP-WM2 - vRsoP-WR2) were also tested. Each of the four mixtures of bacteriophages also showed activity in the same temperature range.

1.2. pH range.

[0085] The lytic activity observed of the characterized bacteriophages against the selected strain of *R. solanacearum* (IVIA-1602.1) tested in different irrigation water, river water, canal water and lake water, was positive in all of the aforementioned types of water at pHs ranging between 6.5 and 9.0. Similarly, the mixtures of bacteriophages showed lytic activity in the same irrigation water and, thus, within the same pH range. The minimum and maximum pH values for the lytic activity of the bacteriophages have not yet been determined.

1.3. Salinity

[0086] Since it has been reported that *R. solanacearum* can grow in the presence of NaCl at concentrations of 1%, and even sometimes up to 2%, the lytic activity of bacteriophages in brackish water of different origins was tested, with salt concentrations of about 1.5%. Lytic activity was observed with all three bacteriophages. The four mixtures of bacteriophages of the invention mentioned in point 1.1 also showed lytic activity in the tested salinity conditions.

1.4. Visible Light

[0087] Since visible light can sometimes affect the lytic activity of bacteriophages, their activity was tested in conditions of light and darkness. It was observed that after 48 hours of uninterrupted exposure to intense light (approximately 15,000 lux), the lytic activity was similar to that observed in dark conditions, so the presence of light does not affect the lytic activity of the bacteriophages of the invention. Similarly, the different mixtures of tested bacteriophages had similar lytic activity both in the presence of light and in darkness.

1.5. Aeration

[0088] Since *R. solanacearum* is an aerobic bacteria and typically grows in liquid medium with stirring (aeration), the effect of the absence of aeration on the lytic activity was determined, as in field conditions aeration is not always assured (by example in tank storage). Activity was observed both in the presence and absence of stirring, of the same magnitude, being faster with aeration. Similarly, the mixtures of the bacteriophages showed lytic activity both with and without aeration.

1.6. Specificity

[0089] Specificity was tested in Petri dishes against bacterial lawns of *R. solanacearum* strains in the LPGA general culture medium, on which two drops of a suspension of each of the three bacteriophages (Fig. 2) were poured. The lytic activity was visualized by the appearance of areas of clearance formed by lysed bacteria in the bacterial lawn where drops of the suspensions with bacteriophages were placed (Fig. 2, corresponding to the test on *R. solanacearum* strain IVIA - 1602.1).

[0090] According to experimental data, the lytic activity of the characterized bacteriophages was positive for 35 strains of *R. solanacearum* of different origins, hosts and years of isolation (Table 1). Among the aforementioned, 13 are international in scope and/or standard. The remaining are all strains isolated in Spain, belonging to the collection of the Valencian Institute of Agricultural Research (IVIA).

Table 1. *R. solanacearum* strains sensitive to the lytic action of the three bacteriophages of the present invention.

STRAIN CODE	COUNTRY OF ORIGIN	HOST	YEAR
International Strains			
NCPPB ^a 1115	United Kingdom (Ex Egypt)	Potato	1961
NCPPB 1584	Cyprus	Potato	1963
NCPPB 2505	Sweden	Potato	1972
NCPPB 2797	Sweden	<i>Solanum dulcamara</i>	1974
BR 264	United Kingdom	<i>Solanum dulcamara</i>	1993
Bordeaux 11-47	France	Aubergine	1994
Nantes 9-46	France	Tomato	1994
550	Belgium (Ex Turkey)	Potato	1995

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(continued)

STRAIN CODE	COUNTRY OF ORIGIN	HOST	YEAR
International Strains			
IPO-1609	Netherlands	Potato	1995
Port 448	Portugal	Potato	1995
W 12	Belgium	Potato	1996
WE 4-96	United Kingdom	River Water	1996
Tom 1	United Kingdom	Tomato	1997
Strains from Spain			
IVIA ^b -1602.1	Canary Islands	Potato	1996
IVIA-2049.53	Canary Islands	Soil	1999
IVIA-2068.58a	Canary Islands	Potato	1999
IVIA-2068.61a	Canary Islands	Potato	1999
IVIA-2093.3.1	Canary Islands	Potato	1999
IVIA-2093.5T.1a	Canary Islands	Potato	1999
IVIA-2128.1b	Castile-Leon	Potato	1999
IVIA-2128.3a	Castile-Leon	Potato	1999
IVIA-2167.1a	Castile-Leon	River Water	1999
IVIA-2167.2b	Castile-Leon	River Water	1999
IVIA-2528.A ₁₋₂	Castile-Leon	River Water	2001
IVIA-2528.A ₃ .1	Castile-Leon	River Water	2001
IVIA-2528.54.A ₂	Castile-Leon	River Water	2001
IVIA-2751.11	Extremadura	River Water	2003
IVIA-2762.1	Extremadura	Tomato	2003
IVIA-2762.4	Extremadura	Tomato	2003
IVIA-3090.1	Andalusia	Tomato	2005
IVIA-3090.5	Andalusia	Tomato	2005
IVIA-3205.A.22	Castile-La Mancha	River Water	2006
IVIA-3243	Andalusia	Tomato	2006
IVIA-3359.9	Castile-La Mancha	River Water	2007
IVIA-3359.10	Castile-La Mancha	River Water	2007
^a NCPPB: National Collection of Plant Pathogenic Bacteria, United Kingdom. ^b IVIA: Bacteria Collection of the Valencian Institute of Agricultural Research, Spain.			

[0091] Strains from the NCPPB are available in this international collection. The other strains are available in the IVIA collection of phytopathogenic bacteria.

[0092] Specificity was also tested against other species of plant pathogenic bacteria and various bacterial isolates of river water to assess the possible impact of the isolated bacteriophages on the microbiota of natural water.

[0093] The lytic activity was negative for the 14 bacterial isolates of river water in the tests, which were selected from various water samples and presented different colonial morphologies from each other and with respect to the host. The activity was also negative for the 11 tested phytopathogenic bacteria strains belonging to other genera, demonstrating the specificity of the selected bacteriophages against *Ralstonia solanacearum*. The same results were obtained with the four possible mixtures of the aforementioned bacteriophages.

- Example 2. Structural Characterization: Morphological and Molecular Characterization.

2.1. Morphological Characterization.

5 **[0094]** A study of the morphology of the selected bacteriophages was carried out via transmission electron microscopy of the viral particles after negative staining with phosphotungstic acid. It is observed that they present the characteristic morphology of the *Podoviridae* family: polygonal, non-enveloped heads 40 to 60 nm in diameter and short tails (Fig. 3). The bacteriophages of this family are also characterized by a genome of double-stranded DNA, a fact which was confirmed in the tests described below.

10 2.2. Molecular Characterization.

2.2.1. Extraction of the DNA of the Three Bacteriophages.

15 **[0095]** Concentrated capsid suspensions were obtained from the three types of bacteriophages from the corresponding bacterial lysates (filtered and treated with DNase and RNase to degrade the bacterial nucleic acids), by polyethylene glycol capsid precipitation protocol. After treatment of the aforementioned capsids with proteinase K, extraction of genomic DNA was performed after the addition of phenol, chloroform and isoamyl alcohol. After confirming that concentration and purity were adequate, the obtained DNAs were analysed by electrophoresis in agarose gel to verify the integrity as a preliminary step to the restriction analysis (see section 2.2.2) and purification for subsequent sequencing (see section 2.2.3).

20 2.2.2. Restriction Analysis of the Genomes of the Three Bacteriophages.

25 **[0096]** From the obtained genomic DNAs of the three bacteriophages, restriction analysis was carried out with various restriction enzymes, chosen to give a banding pattern belonging to T7 genus bacteriophages of the *Podoviridae* family. These enzymes were *KpnI*, *ScaI*, *SpeI* and *XmnI*. *PstI* was also tested because it is an enzyme used to cut the genome of bacteriophages of the species formerly known as *R. solanacearum* described in Japanese Patent JP4532959-B2 (publication number JP2005278513).

30 **[0097]** As shown in Fig 4, the profile bands obtained with these five restriction enzymes is apparently the same for the three bacteriophages: complete digestion with *XmnI* and partial digestion with *KpnI*, *ScaI* and *SpeI* was observed, while no *PstI* digestion was appreciable. These results indicate the genetic proximity of the three bacteriophages to each other, and the difference from the bacteriophages of Japanese patent application JP4532959-B2, whose genomes themselves are cut by *PstI*.

35 2.2.3. Mass Sequencing of Genomic DNAs of the Three Bacteriophages and Bioinformatic Analysis.

40 **[0098]** From the resulting genomic DNA belonging to each of the three bacteriophages, we proceeded to the massive sequencing of the nucleotide bases and subsequent bioinformatic analysis and complete annotation of the genomic sequences found (SEQ ID NO: 1, corresponding to vRsoP-WF2; SEQ ID NO: 2, corresponding to vRsoP-WM2 and SEQ ID NO: 3, corresponding to vRsoP-WR2). This part was entrusted to the Valgenetics, S.L. (University of Valencia Science Park, Valencia, Spain).

[0099] The main findings were as follows:

45 The assembly of sequences obtained by massive sequencing yielded final sequences assembled with 100% fidelity, whose sizes are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Size of the Genomic Sequences Obtained for Each Bacteriophage.

SEQ ID NO:	Bacteriophage	Number of Base Pairs (bp)
1	vRsoP-WF2	40,409
2	vRsoP-WM2	40,861
3	vRsoP-WR2	40,408

55 **[0100]** The results indicated that each of the majority sequences included in the samples of SEQ ID NO: 1 (corresponding to vRsoP-WF2), SEQ ID NO: 2 (corresponding to vRsoP-WM2) and SEQ ID NO: 3 (corresponding to vRsoP-WR2) is readily identifiable as a complete genome of a bacteriophage belonging to the genus of T7-like viruses, which

is the type species of enterobacteria bacteriophage known as T7 (enterobacteria phage T7), which belongs to the *Podoviridae* family.

[0101] Comparing the genomes of the three bacteriophages, it was showed that they were 99% identical over the whole of the genome. However, analysis of these sequences made obvious the presence of small genomic differences such as mutations, insertions and deletions distributed throughout the genome. These differences are higher in the sequence of SEQ ID NO: 2 (corresponding to vRsoP-WM2) than in the sequences of SEQ ID NO: 1 (corresponding to vRsoP-WF2) and SEQ ID NO: 3 (corresponding to vRsoP-WR2), which are almost identical. Thus, the sequence of SEQ ID NO: 2 contains an insertion of 468 nucleotides compared to the sequences of SEQ ID NO: 1 and SEQ ID NO: 3. Fig. 5 shows the sequence alignment extract corresponding to the area of the insertion. Small differences found in the nucleotide sequences indicated that bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 are different bacteriophages of the same viral species (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of the Sequences of the Genomes of Bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2

Compared Sequence (SEQ ID NO:)	Pattern Sequence of the Comparison (SEQ ID NO:)	Coverage*	Identity**
1	2	98%	99%
1	3	100%	99%
2	3	99%	99%

*Homology between sequences of compared genomes, expressed as a percentage.
**Nucleotides matching within areas of homology of the genomes compared, expressed as a percentage.

[0102] Additionally, using the *BlastN* and *Blast2Seq* analyses carried out with the tools accessible to the public via the website of the National Center for Biotechnology Information of the USA (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), it was found that the genomes of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 exhibit some regions with high identity (about 70%) with bacteriophages: *Ralstonia* RSB1, *Vibrio* VP4 and, especially, *Rhizobium* RHEph01, all of them being T7-like bacteriophages (Table 4). These regions (corresponding to 5-23% of the entire genome of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2) belong to highly conserved regions.

Table 4. Comparison of the Sequences of the Genomes of Bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 with Several T7-like Bacteriophage Genomes.

Compared Sequence (SEQ ID NO:)	Genome of the Virus Pattern Sequence of the Comparison (GenBank Access Number)	Coverage*	Identity**
1	Φ <i>Ralstonia</i> RSB1 (AB597179.1)	2%	84%
1	Φ T7 (NC_001604.1)	5%	67%
1	Φ <i>Rhizobium</i> RHEph01 (JX483873.1)	19%	68%
1	Φ <i>Vibrio</i> VP4 (NC_007149.1)	5%	70%
2	Φ <i>Ralstonia</i> RSB1 (AB597179.1)	15%	66%
2	Φ T7 (NC_001604.1)	5%	67%
2	Φ <i>Rhizobium</i> RHEph01 (JX483873.1)	23%	68%
2	Φ <i>Vibrio</i> VP4 (NC_007149.1)	4%	70%
3	Φ <i>Ralstonia</i> RSB1 (AB597179.1)	15%	66%
3	Φ T7 (NC_001604.1)	5%	67%
3	Φ <i>Rhizobium</i> RHEph01 (JX483873.1)	22%	68%
3	Φ <i>Vibrio</i> VP4 (NC_007149.1)	2%	70%

*Homology between sequences of compared genomes, expressed as a percentage.
**Nucleotides matching within areas of homology of the genomes compared, expressed as a percentage.

[0103] These results reveal that, except in these conserved regions within the T7-like bacteriophages, the genomes of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 contain a highly divergent nucleotide sequence with respect to other bacteriophages deposited in GenBank. Therefore, these high differences in nucleotide sequence guarantee that bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 correspond to a new species within the genus of T7-like viruses.

[0104] Moreover, the identification of open reading frames (ORF) and characteristic features of the bacteriophages revealed that the sequences of the genomes of bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2 have genomic organization and ORF expression that is mutually similar, and similar to T7-like bacteriophages in part of the genome (Fig. 6).

[0105] In summary, the three bacteriophages of the present invention are three isolates of the same viral species, being a new species classified as belonging to the genus T7 of the *Podoviridae* family, with organization very similar but distinct from the T7 bacteriophages deposited in GenBank (Fig. 6). The novel bacteriophages have different sequences to T7 bacteriophages, only resembling in some highly conserved areas, such as those related to replication and encapsidation.

- Example 3. Survival of the Three Bacteriophages in Natural River Water.

[0106] The survival of the three selected bacteriophages was tested in two different types of river water: Tormes, from Salamanca, and Turia, from Valencia, both in Spain. These two types of water show substantial differences in the main physico-chemical parameters analysed of the composition: specifically with the water of the Turia River values were comparatively 100 times higher for Mn, 10 times higher for Fe, between 5 and 10 times higher for chlorides and triple for nitrates; with water from the Tormes River, values were approximately 4 times higher in phosphate; the average values of pH were around 8.13 in the water from the Turia River and 7.36 in the water from the Tormes river. Temperature ranges of water ranged from 3.5°C to 20.9°C for the Tormes River and from 11.5°C to 22.0°C for the water from the Turia River, i.e. temperature ranges for both types of environmental water are within the temperature values used for testing survival of the bacteriophages, which were: 4°C, 14°C and 24°C, and the pH values were 7.2 for water from the Tormes River and 8.1 for the water from the Turia River.

[0107] Surprisingly, it was observed that all the bacteriophages maintained their lytic activity against *R. solanacearum* after more than five months under these conditions, in the absence of the host since, prior to inoculation, the water had been filtered through a 0.22 µm filter and autoclaved.

[0108] Fig. 7 shows graphics for the evolution of plaque forming units per millilitre (PFU/ml) of the bacteriophages in both the water from the Tormes River (panel A) and from the Turia River (panel B), in samples incubated at 14°C. It is observed that PFU/ml are maintained in the absence of *Ralstonia solanacearum*. The survival curves of the three bacteriophages samples kept at 4°C and 24°C were similar.

[0109] Thus, it is noteworthy that the three bacteriophages are active and have high lytic activity at all three temperatures tested for more than 5 months.

[0110] In addition, survival and maintenance of the lytic activity of all bacteriophages were confirmed at 4°C and 14°C for a period of time as long as three years. This result is important for conservation within this temperature range when such long storage periods are required.

- Example 4. Biocontrol of Bacterial Wilt Caused by *R. solanacearum*.

4.1. Ability to Control Bacterial Populations in Natural River Water.

[0111] Since the three bacteriophages of the invention had similar lytic activity at the different tested temperatures and pH values in natural water, initially one of them was chosen as a model (bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2) to perform biocontrol tests of bacterial wilt caused by *R. solanacearum*.

[0112] A bacteria-bacteriophage coinoculation test was carried out in sterile river water, in a closed system controlled in the laboratory, for simultaneous quantification of the population levels of both microorganisms over time. To do this, the bacteria was inoculated at a concentration of 10^6 of colony forming units per millilitre (CFU/ml) in the liquid medium (sterile river water) and the bacteriophage was added at a concentration of 10^3 plaque forming units per millilitre (PFU/ml). As shown in Fig. 8, it was confirmed that populations of the inoculated bacteria (reference strain IVIA-1602.1 of *R. solanacearum*) descended substantially in a few hours due to the lytic activity of the inoculated bacteriophages (bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2), the aforementioned pathogenic bacteria virtually disappearing after about 10 hours.

4.2. Tests of Biocontrol of Bacterial Wilt in Host Plants: Bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2.

[0113] The ability of the river water bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2 for biocontrol of the disease caused by *R. solanacearum*

was tested in two independent experiments, watering plants of a susceptible host (tomato plants) with a concentration of the standard bacterial strain IVIA 1602.1 (10^5 CFU/ml) and two different concentrations of the aforementioned bacteriophage (10^6 and 10^9 PFU/ml), and the decimal dilutions (10^5 and 10^8 PFU/ml, respectively), in conditions of optimum temperature and humidity for the development of the disease. The experimental procedure is shown in Fig. 9.

[0114] The results of both experiences are shown in Fig. 10. Overall, the disease incidence decreased to 0-5% in plants irrigated with the pathogen and the bacteriophage, in independent experiments, while in the controls without bacteriophages wilt incidence was 25-50%.

4.3. Tests of Biocontrol of Bacterial Wilt in Host Plants: vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2, vRsoP-WR2, and their Combinations.

[0115] Similar to the experiments of biocontrol in plants carried out with the bacteriophage vRsoP-WF2 described in section 4.2, a macrotest was carried out, which could simultaneously study the ability for biocontrol of each of the three bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2, separately as well as in combinations of two and a mixture of all three. This is considered a macroassay, since it is performed with a large number of plants requiring sufficient room for incubation and people qualified for carrying it out. In all cases, tomato plants, which are a host susceptible to the pathogen, were tested, wherein approximately 35 plants per experimental condition were inoculated, which is approximately 315 plants. Inoculated plants were kept in a climatic chamber of suitable size, in day/night cycles of 16 hours of light at 26°C and 8 hours dark at 22°C and a humidity of about 70%, in conditions of biological containment, in a BSL3 laboratory. In the cited macroassay, the concentration of *R. solanacearum* (strain IVIA 1602.1) in irrigation water was 10^5 CFU/ml, while the total concentration of bacteriophages was 10^7 PFU/ml in all the tested experimental conditions.

[0116] The graph of Fig. 11 shows the results obtained. These results indicate that:

- The bacteriophage vRsoP-WR2 is the most effective of the three, resulting in a greater decrease of bacterial wilt when added to irrigation water at the same concentration as the other two bacteriophages.
- Any mixture of the bacteriophages (either binary combinations, or the combination including the three) are more effective than the separate bacteriophages.

[0117] All these experiments demonstrate the lytic potential of the bacteriophages of the present invention, isolated at different places in Spain, for the biocontrol of *R. solanacearum* and, therefore, the applicability of the aforementioned lytic activity in both the treatment of environmental water for agricultural use that has been contaminated with the aforementioned pathogen, or other uses, such as in the prevention and/or control of the disease caused in the field. This biocontrol ability is especially important, since it is considered that there is currently no effective control methods available via soil or water. And, in this case, as previously discussed and demonstrated in the aforementioned experiments, the biocontrol agents provided by the present invention have the unexpected feature of a high survival rate in water under normal environmental temperatures in Spain, which it is an advantage for use on plants via irrigation water and for the control and prevention of the presence of *R. solanacearum* therein, and for easy and prolonged maintenance of the marketed forms of the bacteriophages of the invention prior to use. Such maintenance may take place in an aqueous medium for a long time without severe loss of lytic activity and not even require, prior to the application to water, pre-dilution of the bacteriophages or their mixtures with any kind of physical or chemical vehicle to facilitate the interaction with the target bacteria or to ensure the stability before coming into contact with it, so that applying bacteriophages to irrigation water, water streams or water reservoirs can be simply by pouring them into *R. solanacearum* contaminated water to be controlled.

Deposit of Microorganisms

[0118] The bacteriophages vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2, with ability to lyse *R. solanacearum* cells, have been deposited in the German Collection of microbial cultures Leibniz-Institut DSMZ-Deutsche Sammlung von Mikro-organismen und Zellkulturen GmbH, Inhoffenstrasse 7B, 38124 Braunschweig, Germany, following the rules of the Budapest Treaty for the deposit of microorganisms for patent purposes, on the following dates and assigned the following access numbers (Table 5).

Table 5. Data on the Deposit of Bacteriophages in the DSMZ German Collection.

Material	Deposit Date	Access Number
vRsoP-WF2	15 April 2015	DSM 32039
vRsoP-WM2	15 April 2015	DSM 32040
vRsoP-WR2	15 April 2015	DSM 32041

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[0119]

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20 SEQUENCE LISTING

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5 gcagatgtcc gagtacacgg gctgtgtcat ggccatcgac ccctcgggcc gtggtgctga 39420
cgagaccggc tacgccatca tcaagattct cgcaggcaac ctcttcctgg tggccgcggg 39480
tggactctcc ggtggctact cagatgaaac tctggagacc ctggcgagac tcgctaagac 39540
10 ccaccaggtg aaccacgtca tcatcgaggc caacttcggt gatggcatgt acaccaagct 39600
catcactcca ttcttcggga aggtgggaca caaggtcctg gtggaggagg tgaagcactc 39660
cacgcagaag gaagcccgta tcatcgacac ccttgagcct gtgctctcga ctcatcgtct 39720
15 catcgttgac cagaaggtca tcgagaacga cttcaggacg gcagagcagg acatcaagta 39780
cagcctgttc taccagatga cccggatcac ccgagacaag ggtgccctgg ctcatgatga 39840
20 ccgtctcgat gcaactggcca tcgctgttgc ctactggacg gagcatatgt ccagggacaa 39900
cgataaggcc gctgctgcca tcaaggacaa ggcgctgaag gatgaactga agaagtctgt 39960
tcacggtgtc cttgggagca aacccaagcg aacctcgtgg atgtcctcga actcaggctc 40020
25 caggtgacat tcggtgccac aataggagaa ccctacgtgg gttcttcggg ggcttcatcc 40080
gtagctgata tggatgccac acaccgtgtg gactcgggaa acctcagtgt gtggtgatgt 40140
agtcgctgca ttctaggaca cccgttagtc tcctattcc tcatctctat ggggggtagg 40200
30 ggggctaact taggtgttcc tagtgttgat gatatagcca ctgagatgtc aacctcagtg 40260
tcccttaagt tgtctcttag ggttgatta aggagacatc atcaccatca tctcccataa 40320
35 ggtcatcctc cccatgttca ctctactagt cctcctctca ggtgtccccg tgggtttcct 40380
tctgggtctc gttctgtatg gcctgttga caactgatgg tgtccctgaa gtgccccctt 40440
agggggaaaa cttccgacgc aaaaatttga aagccccact cgaaattcga cgcgggcaga 40500
40 ttccccccgt gccccccgc ggccccggcc tcgtggcccc tgccgacca cctccgggca 40560
ccctccaggc tgtacgctcc gctgactcc 40589

45 **Claims**

1. A bacteriophage able to lyse cells of *Ralstonia solanacearum* selected from the group of the following:

- 50 a) DSM 32039 (vRsoP-WF2), DSM 32040 (vRsoP-WM2) or DSM 32041 (vRsoP-WR2), or
b) a podovirus whose genome has the sequence of SEQ ID NO: 1 (corresponding to vRsoP-WF2), SEQ ID
NO: 2 (corresponding to vRsoP-WM2) or SEQ ID NO: 3 (corresponding to vRsoP-WR2).

2. A composition comprising at least one of the bacteriophages of claim 1, or combinations thereof.

55 3. The composition of claim 2 comprising one of the following combinations of bacteriophages:

- a) vRsoP-WF2 and vRsoP-WM2;

- b) vRsoP-WF2 and vRsoP-WR2;
- c) vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2;
- d) vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 and vRsoP-WR2.

- 5 **4.** Composition according to claim 3, wherein each of the bacteriophages of the combination is present in the same concentration.
- 5.** Composition according to any one of claims 2 to 4, wherein the total concentration of bacteriophages able to lyse *R. solanacearum* cells varies between 10^2 and 10^9 plaque forming units per millilitre (PFU/ml).
- 10 **6.** Composition according to any one of claims 2 to 5, comprising:
- 15 a) an agronomically acceptable carrier and/or excipient; and/or
 - b) a chemical agent for the control of *R. solanacearum* or a biocontrol agent of *R. solanacearum* different from a bacteriophage of claim 1;
- and which optionally is in the form of a suspension in water or an aqueous solution.
- 20 **7.** Use of a bacteriophage of claim 1 or a composition of any one of claims 2 to 6 for the control of *R. solanacearum* in soil, by adding one or more bacteriophages of claim 1 or a composition of any one of claims 2 to 6 to the soil via irrigation water with which the soil is irrigated, which has been previously treated with one or more of the aforementioned bacteriophages or with the aforementioned composition.
- 25 **8.** Use of a bacteriophage of claim 1 or a composition of any one of claims 2 to 6 for controlling *R. solanacearum* in natural watercourses, channelled water streams, natural reservoirs of water, artificial reservoirs of water, irrigation water and irrigation water reservoirs, which will be used to irrigate crops.
- 30 **9.** Use according to claim 8, wherein the bacteriophage of claim 1 or the composition of any one of claims 2 to 6 is added to a natural reservoir of water or to an artificial reservoir of water, and wherein the water in the reservoir is maintained at a temperature between 4°C and 30°C, or the average water temperature in the reservoir is between 4°C and 24°C, both included.
- 35 **10.** A method for preventing or controlling wilting caused by *R. solanacearum* in a plant, comprising the steps of:
- a) adding a composition of any one of claims 2 to 6 to the water to be used to irrigate the plant;
 - b) watering the plant with said water.
- 40 **11.** Method according to claim 10, wherein the water to which the composition of any one of claims 2 to 6 has been added previously to irrigation, is maintained at a temperature between 4°C and 30°C or an average temperature of between 4°C and 24°C, both included.
- 45 **12.** Method according to any one of claims 10 or 11, wherein the plant is a species belonging to the *Solanaceae* family and is susceptible to and/or tolerant to *R. solanacearum* or any other species susceptible to and/or tolerant to *R. solanacearum*.
- 13.** Method according to claim 12, wherein the plant is selected from the group of potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*), tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*), sweet peppers (*Capsicum annuum*) and aubergines (*Solanum melongena*).
- 50 **14.** Method according to any one of claims 10 to 13, further comprising:
- a) a prior step to the application of the aforementioned method in which the irrigation water is subjected to one or more other strategies such as chemical, physical, and/or biological control for the same plant pathogen or others; and/or
 - b) an optional step in which copper compounds, antibiotics and/or soil fumigants are applied to the soil where the plant is growing.
- 55 **15.** Method according to any one of claims 10 to 14 or the use according to any one of claims 8 or 9, wherein the water

pH is in the range of 6.5 to 9.0, both included.

Patentansprüche

- 5
1. Bakteriophage, der in der Lage ist, Zellen von *Ralstonia solanacearum* zu lysieren, ausgewählt aus der Gruppe der folgenden:
 - a) DSM 32039 (vRsoP-WF2), DSM 32040 (vRsoP-WM2) oder DSM 32041 (vRsoP-WR2), oder
 - 10 b) ein Podovirus, dessen Genom die Sequenz von SEQ ID NO: 1 (entsprechend vRsoP-WF2), SEQ ID NO: 2 (entsprechend vRsoP-WM2) oder SEQ ID NO: 3 (entsprechend vRsoP-WR2) aufweist.
 2. Zusammensetzung umfassend mindestens einen der Bakteriophagen nach Anspruch 1 oder Kombinationen davon.
 - 15 3. Zusammensetzung nach Anspruch 2 umfassend eine von den folgenden Kombinationen von Bakteriophagen:
 - a) vRsoP-WF2 und vRsoP-WM2;
 - b) vRsoP-WF2 und vRsoP-WR2;
 - c) vRsoP-WM2 und vRsoP-WR2;
 - 20 d) vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 und vRsoP-WR2.
 4. Zusammensetzung nach Anspruch 3, wobei jeder der Bakteriophagen der Kombination in der gleichen Konzentration vorhanden ist.
 - 25 5. Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 4, wobei die Gesamtkonzentration der Bakteriophagen, die in der Lage sind, Zellen von *R. solanacearum* zu lysieren, zwischen 10^2 und 10^9 plaquebildenden Einheiten pro Milliliter (PFU/ml) variiert.
 6. Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 5,
 - a) einen landwirtschaftlich annehmbaren Träger und/oder Hilfsstoff; und/oder
 - b) einen chemischen Wirkstoff zur Kontrolle von *R. solanacearum* oder einen biologischen Wirkstoff zur Kontrolle von *R. solanacearum*, der sich von einem Bakteriophagen nach Anspruch 1 unterscheidet;
 - 35 und der gegebenenfalls in Form einer Suspension in Wasser oder einer wässrigen Lösung vorliegt.
 7. Verwendung eines Bakteriophagen nach Anspruch 1 oder einer Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 6 zur Kontrolle von *R. solanacearum* im Boden durch Zugabe eines oder mehrerer Bakteriophagen nach Anspruch 1 oder einer Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 6 zu dem Boden über Bewässerungswasser, mit dem der Boden bewässert wird und das zuvor mit einem oder mehreren der vorgenannten Bakteriophagen oder mit der vorgenannten Zusammensetzung behandelt wurde.
 - 40 8. Verwendung eines Bakteriophagen nach Anspruch 1 oder einer Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 6 zur Kontrolle von *R. solanacearum* in natürlichen Wasserläufen, kanalisierten Wasserströmen, natürlichen Wasserreservoirs, künstlichen Wasserreservoirs, Bewässerungswasser und Bewässerungswasserreservoirs, die zur Bewässerung von Kulturen verwendet werden.
 - 45 9. Verwendung nach Anspruch 8, wobei der Bakteriophage nach Anspruch 1 oder die Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 6 einem natürlichen Wasserreservoir oder einem künstlichen Wasserreservoir zugegeben wird und wobei das Wasser in dem Reservoir bei einer Temperatur zwischen 4 °C und 30 °C gehalten wird oder die durchschnittliche Wassertemperatur in dem Reservoir zwischen 4 °C und 24 °C liegt, beides eingeschlossen.
 - 50 10. Verfahren zur Prävention oder Kontrolle der durch *R. solanacearum* verursachten Verwelkung in einer Pflanze, umfassend die Schritte:
 - a) Hinzufügen einer Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 6 zu dem Wasser, das zur Bewässerung der Pflanze verwendet werden soll;
 - 55

b) Bewässern der Pflanze mit diesem Wasser.

5 11. Verfahren nach Anspruch 10, wobei das Wasser, dem die Zusammensetzung nach einem der Ansprüche 2 bis 6 vor der Bewässerung zugegeben wurde, bei einer Temperatur zwischen 4 °C und 30 °C oder einer Durchschnittstemperatur zwischen 4 °C und 24 °C, beide eingeschlossen, gehalten wird.

10 12. Verfahren nach einem der Ansprüche 10 oder 11, wobei die Pflanze eine Spezies ist, die zur Familie der *Solanaceae* gehört und gegenüber *R. solanacearum* anfällig und/oder tolerant ist, oder jede andere Spezies, die gegenüber *R. solanacearum* anfällig und/oder tolerant ist.

13. Verfahren nach Anspruch 12, wobei die Pflanze aus der Gruppe der Kartoffeln (*Solatum tuberosum*), Tomaten (*Solatum lycopersicum*), Paprika (*Capsicum annuum*) und Auberginen (*Solatum melongena*) ausgewählt wird.

15 14. Verfahren nach einem der Ansprüche 10 bis 13, ferner umfassend:

a) einen vorhergehenden Schritt vor der Anwendung des oben genannten Verfahrens, bei dem das Bewässerungswasser einer oder mehreren anderen Strategien wie chemischer, physikalischer und/oder biologischer Kontrolle desselben oder anderer Pflanzenpathogene unterzogen wird; und/oder

20 b) einen optionalen Schritt, bei dem Kupferverbindungen, Antibiotika und/oder Bodenbegasungsmittel auf den Boden, auf dem die Pflanze wächst, aufgebracht werden.

25 15. Verfahren nach einem der Ansprüche 10 bis 14 oder Verwendung nach einem der Ansprüche 8 oder 9, wobei der pH-Wert des Wassers im Bereich von 6,5 bis 9,0 liegt, beide eingeschlossen.

Revendications

30 1. Un bactériophage capable de lyser des cellules de *Ralstonia solanacearum* sélectionné dans le groupe suivant :

a) DSM 32039 (vRsoP-WF2), DSM 32040 (vRsoP-WM2) ou DSM 32041 (vRsoP-WR2), ou

b) un podovirus dont le génome a la séquence de SEQ ID NO: 1 (correspondant à vRsoP-WF2), SEQ ID NO: 2 (correspondant à vRsoP-WM2) ou SEQ ID NO: 3 (correspondant à vRsoP-WR2).

35 2. Une composition comprenant au moins l'un des bactériophages de la revendication 1, ou leurs combinaisons.

3. La composition de la revendication 2 comprenant l'une des combinaisons de bactériophages suivantes:

40 a) vRsoP-WF2 et vRsoP-WM2;

b) vRsoP-WF2 et vRsoP-WR2;

c) vRsoP-WM2 et vRsoP-WR2;

d) vRsoP-WF2, vRsoP-WM2 et vRsoP-WR2.

45 4. Composition selon la revendication 3, dans laquelle chacun des bactériophages de la combinaison est présent dans la même concentration.

5. Composition selon la revendication 3, dans laquelle chacun des bactériophages de la combinaison est présent dans la même concentration.

50 6. Composition selon l'une des revendications 2 à 5, comprenant :

a) un porteur et/ou excipient agronomiquement acceptable ; et/ou

b) un agent chimique pour la lutte contre *R. solanacearum* ou un agent de biolutte contre *R. solanacearum* autre qu'un bactériophage de la revendication 1;

55 et qui se présente éventuellement sous la forme d'une suspension dans de l'eau ou d'une solution aqueuse.

7. Utilisation d'un bactériophage de la revendication 1 ou d'une composition de l'une des revendications 2 à 6 pour la lutte contre *R. solanacearum* dans le sol, en ajoutant un ou plusieurs bactériophages de la revendication 1 ou une

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composition de l'une des revendications 2 à 6 au sol via l'eau d'irrigation avec laquelle le sol est irrigué, qui a été préalablement traitée avec un ou plusieurs des bactériophages mentionnés ci-dessus ou avec la composition sus-mentionnée.

- 5 **8.** Utilisation d'un bactériophage de la revendication 1 ou d'une composition de l'une des revendications 2 à 6 pour la lutte contre *R. solanacearum* dans les cours d'eau naturels, les flux d'eau canalisés, les réservoirs d'eau naturels, les réservoirs d'eau artificiels, l'eau d'irrigation et les réservoirs d'eau d'irrigation, qui seront utilisés pour irriguer les cultures.
- 10 **9.** Utilisation selon la revendication 8, dans laquelle le bactériophage de la revendication 1 ou la composition de l'une des revendications 2 à 6 est ajouté à un réservoir d'eau naturel ou à un réservoir d'eau artificiel, et dans laquelle l'eau dans le réservoir est maintenue à une température comprise entre 4 C et 30 C, ou la température de l'eau moyenne dans le réservoir est comprise entre 4 C et 24 C, ces deux températures incluses.
- 15 **10.** Procédé de prévention ou de lutte contre la flétrissure causée par *R. solanacearum* chez un végétal, comprenant les étapes consistant à :
- a) ajouter une composition de l'une des revendications 2 à 6 à l'eau devant être utilisée pour irriguer le végétal ;
b) arroser le végétal avec ladite eau.
- 20
- 11.** Procédé selon la revendication 10, dans lequel l'eau à laquelle la composition de l'une des revendications 2 à 6 a été ajoutée avant l'irrigation, est maintenue à une température comprise entre 4 C et 30 C ou à une température moyenne comprise entre 4 C et 24 C, ces deux températures incluses.
- 25 **12.** Procédé selon l'une des revendications 10 ou 11, dans lequel le végétal est une espèce appartenant à la famille des *Solanaceae* et est sensible à et/ou tolérant à *R. solanacearum* ou toute autre espèce sensible à et/ou tolérant à *R. solanacearum*.
- 30 **13.** Procédé selon la revendication 12, dans lequel le végétal est sélectionné dans le groupe des pommes de terre (*Solanum tuberosum*), tomates (*Solanum lycopersicum*), poivrons (*Capsicum annuum*) et aubergines (*Solanum melongena*).
- 14.** Procédé selon l'une des revendications 10 à 13, comprenant en outre:
- 35 a) une étape préalable à l'application du procédé mentionné ci-dessus au cours de laquelle l'eau d'irrigation est soumise à une ou plusieurs autres stratégies telles qu'une lutte chimique, physique et/ou biologique pour le même agent pathogène des végétaux ou autres; et/ou
b) une étape optionnelle au cours de laquelle des composés de cuivre, des antibiotiques et/ou des fumigants de sol sont appliqués au sol dans lequel pousse le végétal.
- 40
- 15.** Procédé selon l'une des revendications 10 à 14 ou l'utilisation selon l'une des revendications 8 ou 9, dans lesquels le pH de l'eau est compris dans la gamme allant de 6,5 à 9,0, ces deux pH inclus.
- 45
- 50
- 55

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

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vRsoP-WF2_ TCCAGAACTTCGCCATGATCCACGACTCCTTCGGGACCACC GCGGGTGACGTGGAGGAGA 8081
vRsoP-WR2_ TCCAGAACTTCGCCATGATCCACGACTCCTTCGGGACCACC GCGGGTGACGTGGAGGAGA 8080
vRsoP-WM2_ TCCAGAACTTCGCCATGATCCACGACTCCTTCGGGACCACC GCGGGTGACGTGGAGGAGA 8159

vRsoP-WF2_ TGTATCGGGTGGTCCGCGAGAGCTTCGTGGAGATGTACTCCGAGGTGCGCGTCCTGGAAG 8141
vRsoP-WR2_ TGTATCGGGTGGTCCGCGAGAGCTTCGTGGAGATGTACTCCGAGGTGCGCGTCCTGGAAG 8140
vRsoP-WM2_ TGTATCGGGTGGTCCGCGAGAGCTTCGTGGAGATGTACTCCGAGGTGCGCGTCCTGGAAG 8219

vRsoP-WF2_ ACTTCCGGGATGAGATCGCGGAGCAACTTTCGAGAAGGCCAAGCGAAGATGCCGCCGC 8201
vRsoP-WR2_ ACTTCCGGGATGAGATCGCGGAGCAACTTTCGAGAAGGCCAAGCGAAGATGCCGCCGC 8200
vRsoP-WM2_ ACTTCCGGGATGAGATCGCGGAGCAACTTTCGAGAAGGCCAAGGCCAAGATGCCCTGATC 8279
***** ** ***** *

vRsoP-WF2_ TACCCGAGCGCGGTCTCCTGGAGTTGTCTCGCGTCTGCGAGAGCCGCTATTGCTTTGC-- 8259
vRsoP-WR2_ TACCCGAGCGCGGTCTCCTGGAGTTGTCTCGCGTCTGCGAGAGCCGCTATTGCTTTGC-- 8258
vRsoP-WM2_ TACCCGCCCCGCGCCTCCTGGAGTTGTCTCGTGTGTGCGAGAGCCGCTACTGTTTTGCGT 8339
**** * ***** ** ***** ** * *****

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ AGACTGTTTTACATTTGCAACTATTCTTATGAGTGAGTGTAAAGTGC GGGGTTGCCT 8399

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ TGGTGCCAGGTGAGAACTGGTATCCGTCCCTCGCAAAGAAGAACAACCAGGTGTGTAAGC 8459

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ GGTGTCACACGGCACGGAGCGAGCGGAAGCGGATTGAAGACCGCGAGACCAACCTCCCGA 8519

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ AGTGGATGCTGCGAAACGCCAGGAATCGGGCCAAGGCACAGGGACTCCCATTGACCTGG 8579

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ AGGAGTCCGACATCCAAATTCGCTCCTCTGTCCCGTCTGCGGATCCCGCTGGAAGTCT 8639

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ CACGCGGGCACITTCACGGACAACCTCCCGGCTCTGGACAAGTTCATCCCGGAGCTTGGGT 8699

vRsoP-WF2_ -----
vRsoP-WR2_ -----
vRsoP-WM2_ ACGTGAAGGGCAACGTGGCCGTCATTTCTCAGAAGGCCAACGTGATGAAGTCCAACGCCA 8759

vRsoP-WF2_ -----CTGAACCCTTCCAC 8273
vRsoP-WR2_ -----CTGAACCCTTCCAC 8272
vRsoP-WM2_ CCATT CAGGAGGTGGAGGCACTGGCCGCGTGGATGCGTAGTCGCGCCTGAACCCTCCAC 8819
***** *****

vRsoP-WF2_ ATCTGGAAGAGTTGAGCCGGGGGAACGATTAGGTGCCACACATGGATAAACCAGCCGCCG 8333
vRsoP-WR2_ ATCTGGAAGAGTTGAGCCGGGGGAACGATTAGGTGCCACACATGGATAAACCAGCCGCCG 8332
vRsoP-WM2_ ATCTGGAAGAGTTGAGCCGGGGGAACGATTAGGTGCCACACATGGATAAACCAGCCGCCG 8879

vRsoP-WF2_ TTCCCCCGGTGGCCTCTCCCGAGACAACCGATGGAACGCAACGAACACGAAGTATCGGAC 8393
vRsoP-WR2_ TTCCCCCGGTGGCCTCTCCCGAGACAACCGATGGAACGCAACGAACACGAAGTATCGGAC 8392
vRsoP-WM2_ TTCCCCCGGTGGCCTCTCCCGAGACAACCGATGGAACGCAACGAACACGAAGTATCGGAC 8939

vRsoP-WF2_ CAGTACGAGTCCGCACTTGGCCGCGCGATTGCTCAGTGGCGCACCGGACGGCCCATCCCG 8453
vRsoP-WR2_ CAGTACGAGTCCGCACTTGGCCGCGCGATTGCTCAGTGGCGCACCGGACGGCCCATCCCG 8452
vRsoP-WM2_ CAGTACGAGTCCGCACTTGGCCGCGCGATTGCTCAGTGGCGCACCGGACGGCCCATCCCG 8999

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

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